

ROLE OF ISLAMIC SOCIAL FINANCE IN REDUCING POVERTY AND ENHANCING ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITYReceived: 04-05-2025
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The study investigates Islamic Social Finance as a voluntary offering in the Islamic Economic system, which plays a significant role in economic sustainability development. Conventional economic programs failed to reduce poverty and income inequality as experienced in the North East, Nigeria. This study uses quantitative research to assess Islamic Social Finance's role in economic sustainability and poverty reduction. Findings indicate that Islamic Social Finance can improve social welfare, reduce income inequality, and lower regional burdens. Further development of Islamic Social Finance is needed for sustainable economic growth and poverty reduction.

Keywords: Islamic Social Finance, Poverty Reduction, Economic Sustainability**Introduction**

One of the critical areas of Islamic Social Finance is Waqf, which means "restraint or imprisonment." In technical terms, Waqf refers to the possession of a particular property, its preservation for limited use or philanthropy, and the prohibition of any use of it for purposes other than those designated (Mahadi, 2022), an essential tool in the Islamic socioeconomic structure which indicates the readiness of the Islamic economics for sustainable development. Islamic social finance, specifically waqf institutions, have offered social welfare services in numerous locations worldwide (Khan & Haneef, 2022). Islamic social finance consists of activities and acts of generosity and religious adherence, which led to the establishment of waqf institutions throughout the Muslim world, alleviating poverty and promoting economic sustainability (Shuaib & Sohail, 2022). In practical terms, poverty reduction refers to a range of economic and humanitarian actions implemented by government agencies, businesses, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to release individuals from poverty permanently (Walter et al., 2024). The research investigated the role of Islamic Social Finance in developing economic sustainability and alleviating poverty, specifically how it can serve as a major supplier of public goods and services. The unique contribution that Waqf, which is seen as a charitable investment for both this world and the hereafter, may make to poverty reduction and sustainability development (Bakr, et al., 2021).

To enhance people's well-being, Waqf can be established in the modern sense by devoting property, furnishings, other moveable goods, liquid assets, and wealth such as cash and shares (Ab Hamid et al., 2024). The term "waqf" refers to any money or valuable asset that a person will donate to Allah for His benefit. Waqf is a feature that requires

consideration due to its extraordinary magnanimity in its fulfillment (Adiguzel & Kuran, 2024).

Waqf property has been abandoned and left unrecorded, and in certain Muslim countries, it has vanished (Bello et al., 2021). Poverty reduction became an issue where almost every state suffered in the country; the government has tried several ways to address the issue; however, the system failed; the study is trying to develop a sustainable way of addressing poverty through Islamic social finance, economic equality, and fostering social cohesion (Hassan et al., 2023). The Islamic economic system is crucial in promoting sustainable economy and social welfare. In this response, the research will explore the concept of Islamic social finance in addressing poverty reduction and enhancing economic sustainability development. The study aims to investigate the vital component of the Islamic economic system, playing a crucial role in promoting social welfare by reducing poverty and creating a sustainable economy.

Literature review

The social economy's sustainability consists of the principles of economic sustainable development that underpin the conventional system, originating from the nearly two-century-old discipline of economics (Salama & Burton, 2022). Economically sustainable manufacturing is a system that can meet present demand levels without endangering future needs (Pimenov et al., 2022). Economic sustainability will be achieved by preserving societal well-being over time. The feeling of well-being is essential to the economic notion of sustainability. Nonetheless, some economic models use money or consumer goods and services from the market to gauge well-being because they have a definite economic value (Sirgy, 2021). This

frequently ignores the non-market outcomes that improve well-being, such as the utility gained from leisure activities, volunteer work, and social interactions supported by several forms of social capital (Mynaříková & Pošta, 2023). Within the Islamic economic system context, all acceptable behaviours, such as volunteer work, charitable endowments, and social connections supported by diverse social capital, are parts of the well-being that Islam recognizes. The social welfare of the public, the Waqf, has become an essential component that directs the shared responsibility of individuals and organizations in cultivating a compassionate environment that builds confidence among stakeholders and guarantees the long-term viability of the Waqf ecosystem (Salama & Burton, 2022). Waqf's contribution to poverty alleviation and economic sustainability Everyone is impacted by poverty. There are several extraordinarily low-income and impoverished people around the globe. Islam has developed several strategies to deal with the problem of poverty in society.

Waqf is one of the long-standing philanthropic customs that Islam established to fight poverty. A society can eliminate poverty through Waqf by implementing different strategies to enable those less fortunate or wealthy to become more self-sufficient, such as providing them with a way to finance their businesses and granting SMEs a loan such as a good loan (Qard Hasan)(Adnan et al., 2021). The fundamental tenets of Islam's card include resource sharing between the affluent and the impoverished, social justice, and inclusion. One of the primary objectives of Islamic finance is the complete prohibition of interest in lending operations (Kamal, 2025). All obligations and loans that come with a financial incentive at the moment of issuance are forbidden. Therefore, the assurance of the Qard is acceptable and highly recommended. The primary objective of Qard-al-Hasan is to assist people experiencing poverty in engaging in the economy ethically and practically soundly(Adiguzel & Kuran, 2024). Therefore, The study examines Islamic Social Finance as a voluntary offering in the Islamic Economic system, which plays a significant role in economic sustainability development.

Reduction of Inequality

Ali (2017) discusses community-driven initiatives within Islamic social finance. It reviews literature on participatory approaches to funding local projects to alleviate poverty, empower the community, and reduce inequality. Karakulah and Muneeza (2024) examined how technological advancements in digital finance enhance Islamic social finance's capability to address disparities. It looks into platforms using blockchain and mobile finance to improve access to social finance tools for the underprivileged. Uddin (2024) focus on the institutional frameworks necessary for the effective functioning of

Islamic social finance. It examines regulatory environments and institutional support mechanisms that enhance the role of Islamic finance in reducing inequality. Aziz and Mohamad's (2016) studies highlight best practices in implementing Islamic social finance initiatives to reduce inequality. It summarizes successful strategies and common challenges while tackling inequality through social finance across different contexts. Islamic social finance's multifaceted role in addressing inequality and poverty issues provides insights into mechanisms, ethical considerations, community approaches, and institutional contexts that shape its effectiveness.

Job Creation

Islamic finance institutions are noted to create job opportunities through various social financing initiatives. For instance, the creation of community development projects funded by waqf has been linked to job creation, directly impacting poverty (Siddiqui et al., 2020). Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are recognized as significant drivers of job creation. Studies show that fostering entrepreneurship through access to financing and support networks enhances innovation and sustainability (Sun et al., 2024). The transition to a green economy has spawned new employment opportunities in renewable energy, conservation, and sustainable agriculture. Literature indicates that fostering green jobs is essential for long-term sustainability (Freire-González, 2018). The impact of automation and artificial intelligence on job markets is widely debated. Some research suggests that while automation displaces specific jobs, it creates new roles that demand different skill sets (Arntz et al., 2019). Policies for workforce retraining and adjusting educational curricula to match future job requirements are essential to sustaining economic growth and job stability (Siddiqui, 2024). Fragmented policy approaches can hinder effective job creation strategies. Comprehensive, coordinated policies that address multiple aspects of sustainability are often recommended (Andreoni, 2024). The intersection of job creation and economic sustainability is multifaceted and requires multidisciplinary approaches. Continued research is needed to bridge gaps in knowledge, especially regarding technology's role in future job markets and the effectiveness of various policy measures. Adopting a holistic view encompassing economic, environmental, and social dimensions will be vital for fostering employment opportunities that contribute to long-term sustainability.

Numerous studies have established a positive correlation between financial inclusion and economic growth. Kara et al. (2021) stated that increased access to financial services enables individuals to invest in education,

healthcare, and entrepreneurial activities, which promote long-term sustainable economic growth. These findings align with Muhammad and Khalil (2021) conclusion that financial inclusion can act as a catalyst for reducing poverty and enhancing economic resilience.

Poverty Reduction

Poverty alleviation is one of the most significant pathways through which financial inclusion contributes to economic sustainability. Jain & Gupta (2023) state that providing access to credit and savings products empowers low-income households to break the cycle of poverty. For instance, microfinance initiatives have successfully offered small loans to entrepreneurial individuals, enabling them to start businesses and improve their livelihoods. Bahadur & Bhandari (2021) noted that access to financial services allows individuals to manage risks, invest in income-generating activities, and prioritize savings. The role of gender in financial inclusion has garnered significant attention in recent literature. Okoli (2024) argues that empowering women through access to financial resources can lead to broad economic benefits, as women reinvest a substantial portion of their incomes in their families and communities. Gill-Wiehl et al., (2022) indicate that microcredit programs targeting women have pronounced impacted household income and nutrition, contributing to more equitable and sustainable economic growth.

Technological Innovations

Recent advancements in technology have played a pivotal role in enhancing financial inclusion. Mobile banking and digital financial services have transformed how individuals access financial products, especially in developing regions. Mavlutova et al. (2022) increased account ownership among low-income populations, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa. Digital platforms reduce transaction costs and improve financial service delivery efficiency, promoting sustainable economic practices. Despite considerable progress, several challenges hinder the full realization of financial inclusion. Barriers such as financial literacy, inadequate regulatory frameworks, and systemic socioeconomic inequalities can impede individuals from accessing financial services (Song et al., 2021). Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated these challenges, as economic disruptions have disproportionately affected vulnerable populations. Research by Goutte and Sanin (2024) emphasizes the need for comprehensive policies that address these issues to foster an inclusive and sustainable financial ecosystem.

Enhancing Economic Sustainability

Social entrepreneurship has emerged as a driver of innovation and sustainability in various sectors, blending traditional business approaches with social mission. This literature review explores how social entrepreneurship contributes to economic sustainability, focusing on key themes such as the definition of social entrepreneurship, its impact on economic performance, the role of social enterprises in addressing social and environmental issues, and the challenges faced in sustaining economic viability. Social entrepreneurship can be defined as the process of identifying and pursuing innovative solutions to social problems while achieving financial sustainability. According to Baquero and Monsalve (2024), social entrepreneurs operate where market failures occur, seeking to create social value alongside economic profit. This dual mission distinguishes social enterprises from traditional for-profit ventures. Utama and Bhatt (2024) emphasize that successful social entrepreneurs possess empathy, resilience, and a strong commitment to their missions.

Numerous studies have demonstrated that social entrepreneurship can enhance economic sustainability by fostering job creation, generating revenue, and stimulating local economies. Qureshi et al. (2023) highlights how social enterprises can create sustainable jobs for marginalized communities, thereby contributing to economic inclusion. Furthermore, as Bataineh et al. (2023) indicated, social enterprises often reinvest profits into community development and social programs, which fosters an ecosystem of sustainable economic growth. Social entrepreneurship directly addresses social and environmental challenges that hinder economic sustainability. For instance, Barth et al. (2021) argue that social businesses focused on environmental sustainability can drive innovation in renewable energy, waste management, and sustainable agriculture. By aligning their business models with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), social enterprises can contribute to broader economic agendas while addressing urgent social needs (Muhammad & Khalil, 2021). Despite the positive impact of social entrepreneurship on economic sustainability, challenges remain. One significant barrier is the difficulty in simultaneously measuring social impact and financial performance (Nguyen, 2024). The lack of standardized metrics can hinder the ability of social enterprises to attract investment and support.

Additionally, many social entrepreneurs face funding challenges due to a reliance on grants and donations, which can undermine long-term financial viability (Shava, 2021). The ecosystem surrounding social entrepreneurship plays a critical role in facilitating or impeding economic sustainability. Government policies incentivizing social enterprises, such as tax breaks and

grants, can enhance financial stability (Gamble & Muñoz, 2021). Moreover, supportive networks and incubators can provide the necessary resources and mentorship for scaling operations (Muathe & Otieno, 2023). The interplay between policy, funding, and market conditions significantly impacts the ability of social enterprises to thrive economically. The concept of resilience in economics has evolved, drawing from theories in ecology and psychology. According to Triplet al. (2024) indicates resilience encompasses adaptability, maintainability, and the ability to transform in the face of change. Economic resilience's multidimensional nature includes the ability to withstand shocks and the capacity for recovery and long-term growth (Zhang et al., 2021). In a sustainable context, economic resilience is linked to the efficient use of resources, social equity, and environmental stewardship. Kennedy and Linnenluecke (2022) outline, economic, social, and environmental interdependencies make resilience a complex but essential characteristic of sustainable economies. Thus, enhancing economic resilience involves fostering diverse economic structures, building adaptable institutions, and promoting social capital.

Economic shocks, whether from financial crises, natural disasters, or global pandemics, have profound and often prolonged impacts on sustainability. Research indicates that such shocks can exacerbate inequalities, disrupt supply chains, and lead to environmental degradation (Yu et al., 2021). Studies have shown that economies with higher resilience tend to sustain their growth trajectories aftershocks (Muhammad & Zanna, 2021). Shava (2021) demonstrated that countries that invested in social safety nets and sustainable infrastructure were more capable of maintaining economic stability during crises. Conversely, economies lacking resilience often experience severe downturns and longer recovery times, reinforcing the need for sustainable practices that enhance resilience (Song et al., 2021).

Researchers advocate for implementing various strategies to foster resilience against economic shocks and promote sustainability. First, diversifying economic activities can reduce dependency on single sectors vulnerable to shocks. For example, Iacobucci and Perugini (2021) emphasizes the role of entrepreneurial ecosystems in diversifying local economies and enhancing resilience. Second, investing in social infrastructure such as education, healthcare, and social safety nets, has been shown to bolster

community resilience. Lopez (2024) enhanced social cohesion and support systems can mitigate the adverse effects of economic shocks, creating more equitable recovery processes. Third, promoting sustainable practices, such as green technologies and resource-efficient production methods, can improve long-term resilience and economic sustainability. Droste et al., (2016) argues that governments should catalyze innovation in sustainable technologies to build a green economy that not only withstands shocks but also thrives on the transition to sustainability. Therefore, the study examines the Islamic Social Finance as a voluntary offering in the Islamic Economic system, which plays a significant role in economic sustainability development.

Methodology

A total of 250 participants were surveyed. The semi-structured questionnaires were conducted and analysed using Structural Equation Modeling using SPSS. The questionnaires were prepared by looking at previous literature during the semi-structured questionnaire (Bryan, 2013). The survey questionnaires were distributed through social media platforms using WhatsApp and physical serving questionnaires from the branches of Islamic Banks. Additionally, Nigeria is recording a significant increase in Islamic economic activities. After considering a face-to-face questionnaire, conducting an investigation using different platforms for accurate justification makes sense. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) is used and the results are analysed based on the sample size requirements.

Data analyses were performed based on confirmatory factor analysis to test the model's effectiveness in addressing economic sustainability in Northern Nigeria. However, the perception of people's relationship between the independent variables and enhancement of Islamic Social Finance and Economic Sustainability. The structural relationship between the standardised burden of the constituent and latent variables was reported based on the goodness of fit index. The indices consist of the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Tucker, Lewis index (TLI). The statistical methods used in this study are descriptive, and frequency analyses were performed to present the demographic variables of the respondents.

Model Assessment of Normality

The test of the variables to justify the normality and worthiness of the data and fitness of the variable-based normality assessment

Table 1.
Assessment of Normality

Construct	Item	Skewness	CR	Kurtosis	CR
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Construct	Item	Skewness	CR	Kurtosis	CR
Reduction of inequality	RI1	-1.304	-7.284	0.448	2.922
	RI2	-0.885	-0.786	0.236	1.358
	RI3	-0.896	-7.399	0.721	3.130
	RI4	-0.787	-6.777	0.691	1.892
Job Creation	JC1	-1.248	-8.679	1.201	3.585
	JC2	-1.276	-8.719	1.387	7.505
	JC3	-1.570	-8.300	1.420	4.730
	JC4	-1.726	-12.219	3.341	13.630
Poverty reduction	PR1	-1.867	-15.516	3.615	13.603
	PR 2	-1.117	-8.439	1.429	4.370
	PR 3	-0.899	-7.136	0.557	2.757
Technological innovation	TI1	-0.608	-8.864	0.691	2.754
	TI2	-1.337	-9.591	0.706	3.248
	TI3	-0.225	-7.257	0.461	1.971
Enhancing ISF and Economic sustainability	EIES1	-1.454	-10.237	1.778	7.250
	EIES 2	-1.658	-9.841	1.569	6.748
	EIES 3	-1.206	-8.885	1.221	4.264
	EIES4	-0.784	-6.437	0.362	0.856
	EIES5	-1.537	-9.791	2.261	8.081
	EIES6	-1.241	-8.507	1.485	4.830
	EIES7	-1.100	-7.693	0.793	3.230
	EIES8	-0.736	-7.355	0.755	3.246
	EIES9	-1.392	-9.285	1.384	5.503

The result of the normality assessment shows the skewness and Kurtosis of all items, as well as the variables placed between ± 2 and ± 2 for skewness, as recommended by Neves *et al.* (2022). Kurtosis is considered ± 7 to ± 7 , as

recommended by Byrne (2013), as the data set of all item constructs was well-modelled by a normal distribution, as both Skewness and Kurtosis have met the threshold.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

Table 2 summarises the demographic information of the respondents, which consists of the demographic areas of the respondents.

Table 2.
Demographic analysis of the respondents

Demographic Data	Categories	Frequency	Percentile
Age	18-35	125	50%
	36-55	75	30%
	56-above	50	20%
Gender	Male	175	70%
	Female	75	30%
Marital status	Single	75	30%
	Married	125	50%
	Widow	50	20%

Demographic Data	Categories	Frequency	Percentile
Educational Level			
	Primary	25	10%
	Secondary	55	22%
	Degree	100	40%
	Postgraduate	45	18%
	Others	25	10%

The study's demographics indicate the respondents' characteristics based on the demographic analysis. The results show that 50 per cent of the respondents are 18 to 35. The Female respondents are 30 per cent, while male respondents are 70 per cent. In addition, the married

category indicates that 50 per cent of the respondents, 30 per cent are single, and 20 per cent are widows. Furthermore, the education level is considered differently, indicating the capacity for knowledge and sound understanding of Islamic Social finance to tackle poverty and enhance economic development in Nigeria.

Table 3.
Description and factor loading

Construct	Measurement	Items used	Loading Factor
RI	Islamic social finance may be used to reduce inequality and promote economic development	RI 1	0.891
	Islamic Social finance may be used to address poverty and economic setbacks in society	RI 2	0.761
	Islamic Social finance addresses the ethical values of restoring the distribution of income	RI 3	0.733
	Waqf can be used to prevent deficit financing by addressing inequality in all sector	RI 4	0.843
JC	Islamic social finance can be used to create jobs and enhance economic development.	JC 1	0.847
	Islamic Social Finance can generate funds, create jobs, and eradicate poverty and literacy.	JC 2	0.703
	Islamic social finance is utilized to formalize the culture of restoring income distribution through empowering youths.	JC 3	0.737
	Islamic social finance can prevent a deficit in the financing budget for job creation and empowerment.	JC 4	0.704
PR		PR 1	0.887
	Poverty reduction can be achieved through Islamic social finance.	PR 2	0.776
	Islamic social finance can address poverty through practical implementation.	PR 3	0.776
TI	Poverty reduction addresses and enhances education setbacks through Zakat	TI 1	0.818
		TI 2	0.777
	Technology can be achieved through Islamic social finance and by eradicating poverty.	TI 3	0.720
ISF-ES	Technology to be achieved through innovation	ISF-ES 1	0.725
	Education Poverty through Zakat and Waqf can address poverty setbacks.	ISF-ES 2	0.651
		ISF-ES 3	0.729
	Restoring distribution income through Islamic social	ISF-ES 4	0.891

Construct	Measurement	Items used	Loading Factor
	finance can address poverty setbacks.		
	Restoring distribution income can be achieved and enhance Islamic social finance towards poverty setbacks.	ISF-ES 5	0.831

Table 3 shows the factor loadings based on the setting of the standardized factor loadings of the five extrinsic variables that appear in the range of >0.5 (Neves *et al.*,

2022); the higher the factor loading and the more positive the construction of the constructs, the lower the factor and the obsolete constructs.

Table 4.
Internal consistency and reliability

Variables	Composite reliability	Cronbach alpha
Reduction of Inequality	0.871	0.853
Job creation	0.826	0.832
Poverty reduction	0.835	0.848
Technological Innovation	0.846	0.852
Enhancing ISF & Economic Sustainability	0.755	0.745

Hair *et al.* (2017) used such a method for the internal consistency of a model. The above Table indicates the composite reliability (CR) of the model's threshold (Hair *et al.*, 2017). Similarly, the composite reliability (CR) value

for all constructs exceeded the recommended value of >0.70, the same as Cronbach's alpha with a value above 0.7, which means the convergent of the constructs analyses is satisfied (Hair *et al.*, 2017).

Table 5.
Discriminant validity

Variables	RI	JC	PR	TI	ISF-ES
Reduction of Inequality	0.536				
Job creation	0.034	0.509			
Poverty reduction	0.022	0.358	0.530		
Technological Innovation	0.132	0.494	0.496	0.549	
Enhancing ISF & Economic Sustainability	0.351	0.227	0.361	0.311	0.419

The discriminant validity results described in Table 5 test the latent structural variables and show the correlation between the latent. The results indicate that all items show good load in different configurations compared to mutual load.

Table 6.
Model of fitness-based theories

Model Fit	Results	Theories
CMIN/DF	3.934	(Hair <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
GFI	0.933	(Byrne, 2013)
AGFI	0.928	(Hair, <i>et al.</i> , 2017).
IFI	0.912	(Hair <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
CFI	0.955	(Hair <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
TLI	0.910	(Byrne, 2013)
RMSEA	0.045	(Hair, <i>et al.</i> , 2017).

Table 6 describes the model's measurement and discloses each fit as indicated above. The CMIN/DF indicates 3.934,

as recommended by Hair *et al.* (2017). The GFI, AGFI, IFI, CFI, and TLI were all recommended to be above 0.9 and

have met the required threshold, while RMSEA is recommended below 0.08, as suggested by Hair *et al.*

(2017). Therefore, the model indicates the level of acceptance.

Table 7.

Hypotheses testing

Path	Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Critical Ratio	P-value	Hypotheses
RI-> ISF-ES	.255	.071	3.591	.001	Supported (H1)
JC-> ISF-ES	.340	.069	4.927	.000	Supported (H2)
PR-> ISF-ES	.203	.052	3.901	.000	Supported (H3)
TI-> ISF-ES	.192	.069	2.781	.008	Supported (H4)

Table 7 testing hypotheses indicates the significant relationship between waqf reducing poverty through Islamic social finance and significantly positive the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 3.591 with an absolute p.value of 0.001. Therefore, the direct link between the RI and ISF-ES is supported (H1). The scenario is the same as the Reduction of Inequality and Enhancement of ISF and Economic Sustainability; the direct link between JC and ISF-ES indicates a positive effect on economic sustainability and accepts H2, H3, and H4. The above results and analyses indicate the direct link between the independent variables and ISF-ES as a direct link with positive effects, as indicated in Table 7.

Following the measurement and structural models investigated, Table 2 indicates the demographic analysis of the respondents. However, Table 3 shows the descriptive factor loading that forms the construct factor loading. Each item used was perfectly loaded above 0.5 as recommended (Hair *et al.*, 2017), which means the higher the factor loading, the more positive the construction of the measurement model. The construct reliability and validity indicate the absolute measurement assessment as all met the threshold of the theories (Hair *et al.*, 2017), composite reliability above 0.7 (Byrne, 2013) and Cronbach's alpha also considered the threshold of 0.7 and above in Table 4 (Hair *et al.*, 2017). Table 5, the discriminant validity results described the square root of AVE as greater than off-diagonal across rows and columns, which were below the recommended threshold of 0.85 (Hair *et al.*, 2014). In addition, Table 6 describes the measurement of the model and discloses each model fit of GFI, AGFI, IFI, CFI, TLI, RMSEA and SRMR as recommended by (Byrne, 2013).

Moreover, Tables 7 indicate the results' direct effect status. The hypotheses on the direct effect between dependent and independent variables were accepted. The study confirmed the relationship between Islamic Social Finance (waqf, zakat, sadaqah and infaq) in enhancing the economic development and sustainability sector and assisting the government policies on reduction of Inequality, Job creation, Poverty reduction, Technological innovation

and enhancing ISF economic justified by (Aziz and Mohamad's, 2016; Karakulah & Muneeza, 2024). Both scenarios showed a positive relationship between the variables and the direct effect. The innovative capabilities of Islamic social finance are the most critical factor for maintaining a competitive advantage in the ISF-ES sector (Shiraz, 2021). The study shows that Islamic social finance can support and sustainability of economic sustainability. The result justifies Islamic social finance's influence on sustainable goals. The structural funding of waqf, zakat, Infaq and Sadaqah established essential benefits and a strong relationship between direct effects, as indicated in Table 7. The result emphasizes the effort to address the vulnerable groups' setbacks and enhance the economic sustainability sector in Northern Nigeria. Finally, the study stresses the significance of applying Islamic Social Finance to economic sustainability in addressing fundamental issues.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

The fitness model of goodness-of-fit, which consists of GFI, AGFI, TLI CFI, and RMSEA (0.052), is perfectly fitted, and model theories were used to meet the required model fit. The empirical evidence demonstrates the statistical fit and the results tested. The direct effect of the hypotheses indicates a positive relationship between variables from H1 to H4. Further, this study discovered a positive relationship between variables. The first set positively influences ISF-ES.

Moreover, the study shows that Islamic social finance significantly reduces poverty, creates jobs, reduces inequality, and creates an avenue of technological innovation, which directly enhances the economy. Therefore, four variables promote the ISF-ES. This study shows that Islamic social finance can be a potential funding source to promote the ISF-ES sector in Northern Nigeria. The study is limited to Northern Nigeria; however, the model can also be utilized in other parts of the world. Future studies can also examine the effect of Islamic social finance on addressing ISF-ES in Nigeria.

5.2. RECOMMENDATION

This will significantly reduce the severe economic setback in Northern Nigeria. The government should utilize Islamic social finance to address economic setbacks and improve society.

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